

Building free education

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Abstract

Building Free Education is a talk that provides an abstract overview of the current educational system virtues and flaws, considers education from a design and architecture point of view and discusses human collective effort to leverage technology in the internet era to build online education. Throughout the first part of the lecture, successes and failures of internet education is presented to provide an intro to discuss about Education 2.0. The lecture will go into analysis of current online platform, conventional schools and failures of MOOCs and similar attempts, and will try to make a parallel observation on economical principles that free software uses.

The talk moves to present a model for "free education", a School 2.0 model that is driven by similar principles to the ones of free software, and which aims to be sustainable for a common, crowdsourced, universal infrastructure that will power knowledge sharing and a new generation of schools. Some of the successes and failures are observed from two free school implementations, *Zamphyr*, which is online, and *Pionir*, an offline free school. The talk is concluded with a call to action and exploration of different segments that interested parties can contribute to.

Keywords: free; open; education; school; MOOC.